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SPOUSAL COMMUNICATION AS CORRELATE OF MARITAL ADJUSTMENT AMONG WORKING CLASS COUPLES IN TARABA AND ADAMAWA STATES, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated how spousal communication relates to marital adjustment among working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria. The research was guided by two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses. A correlational research design was employed. The target population consisted of 98,346 working-class couples across the two states, from which a sample of 398 couples was drawn through a multi-stage sampling technique involving six Local Government Areas. Data were collected using two instruments: the Spousal Communication Questionnaire (SCQ) and the Marital Adjustment among Couples Questionnaire (MACQ). To establish reliability, a pilot test was carried out with 40 couples in Nasarawa State. The instruments yielded Cronbach Alpha coefficients of 0.94 for the SCQ and 0.85 for the MACQ, indicating strong reliability. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions, while linear regression was applied to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. The results indicated significant positive associations between spousal communication and both intimacy and home management. These findings highlight the vital role of effective communication in enhancing marital adjustment. Consequently, the study recommended that couples adopt open and empathetic communication, particularly regarding finances, conflict resolution, and other essential marital domains. It also advised marriage counsellors and family-life educators to integrate communication skills training into marital enrichment programmes.

KEYWORDS: Spousal Communication, Finance, Conflict Resolution, Marital Adjustment, Working Class Couples, Couples.

INTRODUCTION

As a pastor, I have the privilege of counselling numerous couples within and outside my congregation. Over the years, I have observed a growing concern, many couples struggle with the issue of adjustment in their marital relationship. I have witnessed couples who despite their love for each other, struggle to communicate effectively over finance, conflict resolution, intimacy among others, leading to feelings of frustration and maladjustment. My observations led me to wonder, what are the underlying factors contributing to lack of adjustment among married couples? How can couples develop effective communication strategies to navigate life's challenges? What role does communication play in fostering marital adjustment? These questions sparked my interest in exploring the complex dynamics of spousal communication and marital adjustment.

In recent years, married couples seem to be having marital challenges. The researcher observed that, many married couples struggle to keep maintain their marital relationship. This seems to be a global concern. The researcher delved into this research to see if there can be a solution to some of these challenges, particularly among working-class couples. Despite having stable employment and educational exposure, many couples still encounter challenges in key areas such as managing finances, resolving conflicts, maintaining intimacy, balancing religious values, handling domestic responsibilities, and supporting each other's careers. These

challenges often result in frequent misunderstandings, emotional disconnection, and poor marital adjustment.

Marital adjustment is a critical concern in contemporary society, with growing reports of marital instability, dissatisfaction, and eventual divorce affecting couples across the globe. In the United States, Whisman, Dixon, and Johnson (2017) reported that approximately 10–15% of marriages face significant distress, often rooted in issues such as communication breakdown, financial disagreements, lack of intimacy, and unresolved conflicts. Similar trends are seen in parts of Europe and Asia, where evolving societal roles, economic pressures, and emotional disconnect have strained marital relationships. In Africa, the story is not different. In countries such as Kenya and Nigeria, factors such as spousal disagreements, domestic violence, conflicting career demands, and religious differences have been implicated in rising marital instability (Ngure & Muhia, 2013). Traditional gender roles, economic hardship, and extended family interference further complicate these dynamics. In Nigeria specifically, changing societal expectations and urban pressures have increased the burden on marital unions, especially among the working-class population who must juggle professional responsibilities with domestic expectations. While a number of factors have been identified as contributors to marital maladjustment including financial strain, sexual dissatisfaction, and external

interference recent scholarship and observation suggest that spousal communication may play a significant role in marital adjustment. Despite cultural, social, or economic differences, couples who communicate effectively are more likely to experience harmony, cooperation, and emotional intimacy in their relationships.

Spousal communication thus, refers to the verbal and non-verbal exchange of ideas, emotions, and expectations between partners. It is central to emotional bonding, conflict resolution, and mutual understanding. According to Floyd (2016), effective communication involves both expressive and receptive skills, allowing couples to share their thoughts while actively listening to one another. In marriage, communication functions as a tool for building trust, intimacy, and a shared vision for the family.

Spousal communication might enhance marital adjustment, especially among working-class couples who face unique social and occupational pressures. According to Esere, Yeyeodu and Oladun (2014), communication is crucial in all human existence, especially marriage; the authors submitted that effective communication is essential for a healthy relationship because it enables partners to feel love, trust, tolerance, patience, and have the ability to manage conflict.

Marital adjustment refers to the continuous process by which spouses modify their behaviour, attitudes, and expectations in order to maintain harmony, satisfaction, and mutual understanding in the

relationship. It involves the ability to adapt to daily challenges and changing roles that naturally arise within a marital setting (Makvana, 2014). For marriages to thrive, couples must effectively adjust in several key areas of their shared lives. This study conceptualizes marital adjustment across six core dimensions: finance, conflict resolution, intimacy, home management, religion, and career. Each of these dimensions is central to marital functioning and heavily reliant on effective spousal communication. Where communication is poor, maladjustment tends to emerge, often leading to marital dissatisfaction, emotional disconnect, or instability.

One of the most significant areas where couples must achieve adjustment is finance. Financial issues are a common source of stress and conflict in marriages worldwide. Financial adjustment involves how partners manage income, savings, expenditures, and budgeting to achieve stability (Papp & Cummings, 2015). Many couples avoid discussing financial problems or fail to plan together, leading to unmet expectations and anxiety. This concern might not be different from the experience of working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, where economic challenges and income instability are common.

Closely tied to financial stress is the issue of conflict resolution. Disagreements are natural in every relationship, but successful marital adjustment depends on how couples handle these disagreements. Conflict resolution entails the ability to identify problems, express grievances respectfully, and negotiate mutually satisfying solutions.

Ogunyemi (2017) noted that the lack of open and respectful communication is a major barrier to conflict resolution which might not be different in marriage. Couples who avoid discussing sensitive issues or who react aggressively are less likely to resolve their conflicts constructively. These kinds of difficulties are not unique to any one group and may similarly affect working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States.

- **Statement of the Problem**

Marital maladjustment is becoming an increasingly disturbing trend across societies, as many couples today face serious challenges that threaten the stability and satisfaction of their relationships. Common issues such as unresolved conflicts, lack of emotional closeness, disagreements over finances, and growing disconnection are now more evident in homes than ever before. These difficulties, if not addressed, often result in emotional distress, strained family life, separation, and even divorce. The social and psychological consequences of unstable marriages affect not only the spouses but also the well-being of children and the larger society.

While several factors have been attributed to marital breakdowns, including economic hardship, lifestyle differences and spousal communication has continued to surface as a fundamental element that influences how well couples adjust in their relationship. Many couples struggle in silence because they lack the ability or willingness to communicate openly, respectfully and

consistently. This becomes more evident in critical areas of marital life where adjustment is needed. Poor communication about financial responsibilities can lead to mistrust and misunderstanding. Inability to manage conflicts constructively often escalates simple disagreements into long-term resentment. Intimacy is weakened when couples cannot express their emotional and physical needs. The home front becomes unbalanced when roles and responsibilities are not discussed and shared. Differences in religious beliefs and practices create tension when they are not respectfully addressed, and career-related decisions cause friction when not openly communicated.

These challenges are not limited to any one group and might not be different from the experiences of working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, where professional demands, economic constraints, and cultural diversity may further complicate marital relationships. However, there is a noticeable need in existing research to the best of the researcher's knowledge particularly in these states, regarding how spousal communication relates to marital adjustment across key areas of married life. Most studies have examined marital communication and satisfaction in general terms, without exploring how communication influences specific domains such as finance, conflict resolution, intimacy, home management, religion, and career. It is against this background that this study sought to examine the relationship between spousal

communication and marital adjustment among working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States.

- **Purpose of the Study**

The purpose of this study was to examine spousal communication as correlate of marital adjustment among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the relationship between spousal communication and finance among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria.
2. find out the relationship between spousal communication and conflict resolution among couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria.

- **Research Question**

The following questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the relationship between spousal communication and finance among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria?
2. How does spousal communication correlate with conflict resolution among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria?

- **Hypotheses**

The following hypotheses are formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Spousal communication has no significant relationship with finance among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria.
2. Spousal communication has no significant relationship with conflict resolution among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design, a non-experimental approach used to examine the strength and direction of relationships between variables without altering them. The research was carried out in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria, with a total population of 98,346 working-class couples — 42,897 in Taraba and 55,449 in Adamawa (Departments of Establishment and Manpower Planning, 2024). From this population, 398 couples were selected from six Local Government Areas.

Two researcher-developed instruments were used for data collection: the Spousal Communication Questionnaire (SCQ) and the Marital Adjustment Couples Questionnaire (MACQ). The SCQ assessed the effectiveness of communication between spouses and consisted of two sections; Section A captured demographic information, while Section B evaluated communication across diverse marital domains such as emotional sharing, conflict resolution, financial discussions, intimacy, household duties, decision-making, spiritual beliefs, and overall relational well-being. Responses were rated on a four-point scale from Never (1) to Always (4). The MACQ measured marital adjustment in six major

areas: finance, conflict resolution, intimacy, home management, religion, and career. Each cluster contained at least seven items, and responses were also rated on a four-point scale, with higher scores indicating better adjustment in each domain. Instrument reliability was confirmed through a pilot test involving 40 working-class couples in Nasarawa State. The SCQ produced a reliability coefficient of 0.94, while the MACQ recorded 0.85; its cluster coefficients ranged from 0.76 to 0.94. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to address the research questions, following APA (2010) guidelines for interpreting correlation strength. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses, determine whether relationships existed between spousal communication and the different marital

adjustment indices, assess the nature of those relationships, and verify their statistical significance at the 0.05 level.

FINDINGS

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between spousal communication and finance among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria?

Table 1 shows that the Pearson Correlation Coefficient between spousal communication and finance is .822, indicating a strong positive relationship. This means that higher levels of spousal communication are associated with better financial adjustment among working-class couples.

Table 1: Relationship Between Spousal Communication and Finance Among Working-Class Couples

		Spousal Communication	Finance
Spousal Communication	Pearson Correlation	1	.822**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Finance	Pearson Correlation	.822**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Research Question 2: How does spousal communication correlate conflict resolution among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria?

communication and conflict resolution is .732, indicating a strong positive relationship. This result suggests that as spousal communication improves, the couples' ability to manage and resolve conflicts also increases.

Table 2 shows that the Pearson correlation coefficient between spousal

Table 2: Relationship Between Spousal Communication and Conflict Resolution Among Working-Class Couples

		Spousal Communication	Conflict Resolution
Spousal Communication	Pearson Correlation	1	.732**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Conflict Resolution	Pearson Correlation	.732**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

- **Testing of Hypotheses**

among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: Spousal communication has no significant relationship with finance

Table 3: Linear Regression Showing Relationship between Spousal Communication and Finance Among Working Class Couples

Variables	R	R²	df	F	β	T	Sig.	Decision
Constant	.822	.676	396	825.289		7.578	.000	
Finance					.822	28.728	.000	Significant

Table 3 shows that the regression result yielded an R value of .822 and R² of .676, indicating that spousal communication accounts for 67.6% of the variance in financial adjustment. The F-value (825.289) is statistically significant at p = .000. The beta ($\beta = .822$) and t-value (28.728) also show a strong predictive relationship between spousal communication and finance. Since the p-value is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means spousal

communication has significant relationship with financial adjustment among working-class couples, implying that improved communication is a strong contributor to financial cooperation, transparency, and budgeting harmony between partners.

Hypothesis 2: Spousal communication has no significant relationship with conflict resolution among working class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria.

Table 4: Linear Regression Showing Relationship between Spousal Communication and Conflict Resolution Among Working Class Couples

Variables	R	R ²	df	F	β	T	Sig.	Decision
Constant	.732	.535	396	456.049		10.238	.000	Significant
Conflict resolution					.732	21.355	.000	

Table 4 shows that the regression analysis produced an R = .732 and R² = .535, indicating that spousal communication explains 53.5% of the variation in conflict resolution. The F-statistic (456.049) is significant at p = .000. The beta coefficient ($\beta = .732$) and corresponding t-value (21.355) further confirm this significant relationship. Given that the significance value is below .05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that spousal

communication has a significant relationship with conflict resolution.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the analyzed data the following findings are discussed;

The first hypothesis revealed that spousal communication has a significant relationship with finance among working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria. This finding means that

when couples maintain open, respectful, and consistent communication, they are more likely to make joint financial decisions, plan budgets together, manage debts, and agree on financial goals. Such communication fosters financial transparency and builds mutual trust, reducing the chances of misunderstandings, financial secrecy, or unilateral decision-making. In many relationships, money is a sensitive topic and when poorly handled, it becomes a major source of conflict. The finding agrees with the work of Papp and Cummings (2015), who found that constructive communication about finances helps couples establish shared goals and strategies that strengthen their economic partnership. Similarly, Dew and Dakin (2011) observed that effective financial communication significantly reduces financial strain and marital tension. This finding is justified because financial matters touch nearly every aspect of family life—education, health, lifestyle, and long-term planning. When couples fail to communicate openly about income, expenses, or priorities, mistrust and resentment can build. Conversely, when communication is open and decisions are made collaboratively, couples feel more secure, valued, and aligned in their future planning. This sense of unity in handling finances creates a platform for greater marital stability and satisfaction.

The second hypothesis revealed that spousal communication has a significant relationship with conflict resolution among working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States. This means that couples

who are able to communicate calmly, clearly, and empathetically are better positioned to address disagreements without escalation. Such communication enables partners to express concerns, listen to each other's viewpoints, and seek compromises, thus resolving issues in a constructive rather than destructive way. The finding agrees with the work of Okafor (2019), who found that conflict resolution is more successful when couples utilize effective communication strategies such as active listening and assertive expression. Similarly, Ogunyemi (2017) found that open communication is central to understanding the root causes of conflict and arriving at solutions that satisfy both partners. This finding is justified because unresolved conflicts, especially when poorly communicated, can fester and damage the emotional fabric of the relationship. In contrast, healthy communication creates a non-threatening space where issues can be tackled without blame or hostility. It also fosters mutual respect, reduces emotional distress, and strengthens the couple's ability to face future challenges together. Effective conflict resolution, grounded in effective communication, is thus a critical component of marital adjustment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that spousal communication plays a critical and significant role in shaping various dimensions of marital adjustment among working-class couples in Taraba and Adamawa States, Nigeria. The results demonstrated that effective communication

between spouses was positively related to financial harmony, and successful conflict resolution. These outcomes underscore the importance of open, honest, and respectful communication in fostering mutual understanding, reducing marital stress, and enhancing overall relationship satisfaction. Thus, the study highlights spousal communication as a vital interpersonal tool that not only promotes individual well-being but also contributes to the stability and functionality of the marital union across multiple life domains.

- **Recommendations**

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to enhance marital adjustment through effective spousal communication among working-class couples:

- Counsellors should encourage couples to engage in transparent financial communication, including discussions about income, budgeting, savings, and spending, to prevent financial misunderstandings and foster joint decision-making.
- Marriage counsellors and family life educators should train couples in constructive communication techniques such as active listening, empathy, and negotiation, to help them in conflict resolutions.

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